

Sm/ZrCl₄ induced reductive cleavage of Te-Te bond in diaryl ditellurides : A novel method for the synthesis of unsymmetrical tellurides

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Diaryl ditellurides are reduced by the system of Sm/ZrCl₄ to produce samarium aryltellurolates which react with alkyl halides to afford tellurides.

Organotellurium compounds have received considerable attention as useful synthetic reagents and intermediates in organic synthesis¹. While there are many methods for the introduction of a tellurium moiety into organic molecules, the use of tellurium anions is especially convenient and common². The use of ditellurides and samarium diiodide in THF/HMPA has also recently been reported to give telluride anion³.

As a powerful, versatile and ether-soluble one-electron transfer reducing agent, SmI₂ has played an ever-increasing role in organic synthesis since its introduction by Kagan and his group⁴. Samarium diiodide promotes a number of important individual reactions found useful in organic synthesis⁵. Though SmI₂ is a useful reagent, its storage is difficult because it is very sensitive to air-oxidation. On the other hand, metallic samarium is stable in air and its strong reducing power (Sm³⁺/Sm = -2.41 V) is similar to that of magnesium (Mg²⁺/Mg = -2.37 V), superior to that of zinc (Zn²⁺/Zn = -0.71 V). These properties prompted us to use the more convenient and cheaper metallic samarium directly instead of samarium(II) iodide. There are some recent reports on the direct use of Sm in organic synthesis⁶. Herein, we report that reductive cleavage of Te-Te bond in ditellurides by Sm/ZrCl₄ system leads to telluride anion species, which reacts with alkyl halides to give unsymmetrical tellurides in good yields under mild and neutral condition.

The formation and reaction of samarium aryltellurolates, formed *in situ* from the cleavage of the corresponding ditellurides with Sm/ZrCl₄ reductive system, are as follows :

The formation of tellurolate anion species with Sm/ZrCl₄ is similar³ to that with SmI₂.

The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Sm/ZrCl₄ mediated reaction of ditellurides with alkyl halides

Compd. no.	Ar	RX	Product	Yield ^a %
1	Ph	PhCH ₂ Cl ^b	PhTeCH ₂ Ph	81
2	Ph	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₅ Br	PhTe(CH ₂) ₅ CH ₃	75
3	Ph	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₇ Br	PhTe(CH ₂) ₇ CH ₃	72
4	Ph	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₉ Br	PhTe(CH ₂) ₉ CH ₃	66
5	Ph	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₁ Br	PhTe(CH ₂) ₁₁ CH ₃	70
6	Ph	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₅ Br	PhTe(CH ₂) ₁₅ CH ₃	71
7	Ph	(CH ₃) ₂ CHBr	PhTeCH(CH ₃) ₂	56
8	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₆ Br	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ Te(CH ₂) ₆ CH ₃	74
9	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₅ Br	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ Te(CH ₂) ₅ CH ₃	76
10	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₃ Br	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ Te(CH ₂) ₃ CH ₃	76

^aIsolated yield based on ArTe-TeAr. ^bRoom temp., 4 h.

Experimental

M.ps. were obtained on an electrothermal apparatus and are uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 80 MHz instrument using carbon tetrachloride used as the solvent and tetramethylsilane as an internal standard, and IR spectra on a PE-683 spectrophotometer.

Tetrahydrofuran was freshly distilled from sodium benzophenone ketyl before use. Alkyl halides (commercial) were used as such. The reactions were performed in a Schlenk type glass apparatus and under a nitrogen atmosphere.

General procedure : A mixture of samarium powder (0.15 g, 1 mmol; 99.9%), zirconium tetrachloride (0.04 g, 0.2 mmol) and ditelluride (0.5 mmol) was flushed with nitrogen and tetrahydrofuran (10 ml) added. The mixture was stirred at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere. The red solution gradually turned brown within 2 h, which showed that the Te-Te bond had been reductively cleaved by Sm/ZrCl₄ and that samarium aryltellurolate (ArTeSmCl₂) generated. Alkyl halides (1 mmol) were then added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10 h. Then dil. HCl (20 ml) and diethyl ether (50 ml) were added. The or-

ganic layer was washed with water (2×20 ml) and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the crude product purified by preparative TLC on silica gel using light petroleum : ethyl acetate (100 : 1) as eluent.

The advantages of the present procedure are single product, simple manipulation, mild and neutral conditions.

The spectral data of compounds (1-10) are as follows : **1**⁷, m.p. 33–34°, δ_{H} 3.95 (2H, s), 6.80–7.70 (10H, m), $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3080, 3050, 2950, 1580, 1560, 1500, 1480, 1250, 1160, 1020, 760, 740, 690; **2**⁸, oil, δ_{H} 0.83 (3H, t), 1.10–1.40 (8H, m), 2.73 (2H, t), 6.90–7.16 (3H, m), 7.40–7.66 (2H, m), $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3085, 3070, 2980, 2960, 2860, 1580, 1480, 1450, 1440, 1380, 1300, 1150, 1060, 1020, 1000, 720, 685, 650; **3**⁸, oil, δ_{H} 0.83 (3H, t), 1.20–1.41 (12H, m), 2.74 (2H, t), 6.85–7.18 (3H, m), 7.42–7.70 (2H, m), $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3080, 3070, 2980, 2960, 2860, 1580, 1480, 1450, 1380, 1300, 1150, 1060, 1020, 1000, 725, 685, 650; **4**⁷, oil, δ_{H} 0.83 (3H, t), 1.20–1.40 (16H, m), 2.73 (2H, t), 6.90–7.16 (3H, m), 7.40–7.66 (2H, m), $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3085, 3070, 2980, 2960, 2860, 1580, 1480, 1460, 1440, 1380, 1300, 1150, 1060, 1020, 1000, 720, 685, 650; **5**⁹, oil, δ_{H} 0.81 (3H, t), 1.05–1.45 (20H, m), 2.75 (2H, t), 6.95–7.15 (3H, m), 7.45–7.78 (2H, m), $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3085, 3065, 2980, 2960, 2870, 1585, 1560, 1475, 1460, 1440, 1380, 1020, 1000, 720, 685, 650; **6**⁸, m.p. 32–33°, δ_{H} 0.80 (3H, t), 1.06–1.45 (28H, m), 2.74 (3H, t), 6.95–7.15 (3H, m), 7.45–7.78 (2H, m), $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3080, 3065, 2980–2960, 2870, 1585, 1560, 1480, 1440, 1380, 1020, 1000, 720, 690, 650; **7**^{3b}, oil, δ_{H} 1.30 (6H, d), 3.50–3.70 (1H, m), 7.10–7.30 (3H, m), 7.40–7.60 (2H, m), $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3085, 3070, 2980, 2960, 2860, 1580, 1480, 1450, 1440, 1380, 1300, 1150, 1060, 1020, 1000, 720, 685, 650; **8**¹⁰, oil, δ_{H} 0.85 (3H, t), 1.15–1.45 (10H, m), 2.25 (3H, s), 2.75 (2H, t), 6.80–6.90 (2H, m), 7.40–7.55 (2H, m), $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3085, 3070, 2980, 2960, 2860, 1580, 1480, 1450, 1440, 1380, 1300, 1220, 1120, 1010, 800, 770; **9**¹¹, oil, δ_{H} 0.86 (3H, t), 1.15–1.45 (8H, m), 2.25 (3H, s), 2.75 (2H, t), 6.80–6.90 (2H, m), 7.40–7.55 (2H, m), $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3085, 3070, 2980, 2960, 2860, 1580, 1480, 1450, 1440, 1380, 1300, 1220, 1120, 1010, 790, 770; **10**¹¹, oil, δ_{H} 0.87 (3H, t), 1.15–1.45 (4H,

m), 2.25 (3H, s), 2.75 (2H, t), 6.80–6.90 (2H, m), 7.40–7.55 (2H, m), $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3085, 3070, 2980, 2960, 2860, 1580, 1480, 1450, 1440, 1380, 1300, 1220, 1120, 1010, 790, 770.

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